

MY JOURNEY

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Sergio Leal

**My Journey at the Public Works Academy:
A Hands-On Experience**

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Summary

The essay recounts a student's comprehensive educational journey at the Public Works Academy, highlighting experiences in quality control across various disciplines. It covers soil, asphalt, and concrete testing, CDL practice, surveying, FEMA experiences, and stormwater inspections. Through theoretical learning and practical application, the student gains expertise in assessing soil quality, testing asphalt and concrete durability, operating heavy machinery, conducting accurate surveys, and ensuring compliance with regulatory standards. The essay underscores the transformative nature of the academy's training, equipping the student with the skills and dedication needed for a successful career in public works.

Keywords

Quality control, soil testing, Abraham concrete slump test, asphalt testing, concrete testing, cdl practice, surveying, FEMA Inspections, stormwater inspections

My Journey at the Public Works Academy: Mastering Quality Control in Soil, Asphalt, Concrete, CDL Practice, Surveying, FEMA, and Stormwater Inspections

My time at the Public Works Academy has been an incredible journey of learning, hands-on experience, and personal growth. This journey has equipped me with a comprehensive understanding of quality control in various critical areas such as soil, asphalt, and concrete testing, CDL practice, surveying, FEMA inspections, and stormwater inspections. Each facet of my training has been essential in shaping my skills and knowledge, preparing me for a future in public works.

Quality Control in Soil Testing

Soil testing is fundamental in public works, as it ensures that the ground can support infrastructure projects. My experience began with learning the theoretical aspects of soil properties and classification. We delved into the various types of soil, their composition, and how their characteristics affect construction projects.

Fieldwork involved conducting various tests to assess soil quality. One of the primary tests we performed was the Proctor compaction test, which determines the optimal moisture content at which soil achieves its maximum density. This test is crucial for understanding how soil will behave under load. Additionally, we performed Atterberg limits tests to determine the plasticity of soil, which helps in classifying soil types and predicting their behavior under different moisture conditions.

These tests were often conducted in a laboratory setting, where we used equipment like sieves for particle size analysis and moisture meters for determining water content. The precision and meticulous attention to detail required in soil testing taught me the

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importance of thoroughness in quality control, as even minor inaccuracies can lead to significant issues in construction projects.

Quality Control in Asphalt Testing

Asphalt testing is another critical component of public works, particularly for road construction and maintenance. My training included learning about the properties of asphalt and the various tests used to ensure its quality. We conducted the Marshall stability test to determine the strength and durability of asphalt mixtures, which is essential for ensuring that roads can withstand heavy traffic and environmental conditions.

Field inspections involved monitoring the temperature of asphalt during paving and ensuring proper compaction using rollers. We also performed asphalt content tests to verify that the correct proportion of bitumen was used in the mixture. These practical experiences reinforced the importance of precision in asphalt testing, as any deviation from the specified standards can lead to premature road failure.

Quality Control in Concrete Testing (Abraham Concrete Slump Test)

Concrete testing was a significant part of my training, with a particular focus on the Abraham Concrete Slump Test. This test measures the workability and consistency of fresh concrete, which is crucial for ensuring that it can be properly placed and compacted without segregation.

In the field, we conducted slump tests by filling a slump cone with fresh concrete and measuring the subsidence of the concrete after the cone is removed. This test provided immediate feedback on the concrete's consistency and workability. We also performed

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compressive strength tests by casting concrete cylinders and testing them under controlled conditions to determine their ability to withstand loads.

These tests highlighted the importance of maintaining strict quality control standards in concrete production and placement. Any inconsistencies in the mix can lead to weaknesses in the finished structure, emphasizing the need for rigorous testing and monitoring.

CDL Practice

Obtaining a Commercial Driver's License (CDL) was another crucial aspect of my training. The CDL certification is essential for operating heavy machinery and vehicles used in public works projects. Our training included both theoretical lessons on vehicle operation and safety, and practical driving sessions.

We practiced maneuvering large vehicles, performing pre-trip inspections, and understanding the regulations governing commercial driving. The practical training involved driving on various terrains and conditions, which prepared me to handle the heavy equipment used in construction and maintenance tasks. The CDL training was challenging but immensely rewarding, as it provided me with the skills to operate essential machinery safely and efficiently.

Surveying

Surveying is fundamental to planning and executing public works projects. My training in surveying included learning to use various instruments such as theodolites, total stations, and GPS units to measure distances, angles, and elevations.

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Field exercises involved creating topographic maps, staking out construction sites, and verifying the alignment of structures. These tasks required a keen eye for detail and a solid understanding of geometry and trigonometry. Surveying taught me the importance of accuracy and precision in laying the groundwork for successful construction projects, as any errors can lead to significant issues during construction.

FEMA and Stormwater Inspections

My training also included conducting FEMA (Federal Emergency Management Agency) inspections and stormwater inspections. FEMA inspections are critical for assessing damage and ensuring compliance with federal regulations after natural disasters. We were trained to evaluate the structural integrity of buildings, document damage, and recommend necessary repairs.

Stormwater inspections focused on managing runoff and preventing pollution. We learned to inspect stormwater management systems, such as detention basins and drainage ditches, to ensure they functioned correctly. We checked for signs of erosion, sediment buildup, and proper vegetation management. Understanding the environmental impact of stormwater runoff and the importance of sustainable practices was a key takeaway from these inspections.

Integrating Experiences and Looking Ahead

Each of these experiences—soil, asphalt, and concrete testing, CDL practice, surveying, FEMA inspections, and stormwater inspections—has provided a comprehensive education in public works. The academy's blend of classroom instruction and hands-on training has prepared me for the multifaceted challenges of a

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career in this field. I have developed a strong foundation in quality control, an essential aspect of ensuring the safety and durability of public infrastructure.

Looking ahead, I am eager to apply these skills in a professional setting. The diverse training, I have received has equipped me with the technical knowledge and practical experience needed to contribute effectively to public works projects. Whether it's ensuring the proper compaction of soil, testing the quality of asphalt and concrete, conducting accurate surveys, or inspecting stormwater systems, I am confident in my ability to perform these tasks to the highest standards.

In summary, my journey at the Public Works Academy has been transformative. It has instilled in me a deep respect for the meticulous processes involved in building and maintaining public infrastructure. I am grateful for the opportunities to learn from experienced professionals, work with advanced equipment, and participate in real-world projects. As I prepare to embark on my career, I carry with me the knowledge, skills, and dedication to making a positive impact in the field of public works.

Appendix

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This table provides a concise overview of your experiences in each aspect of public works, along with the skills acquired through each activity. Performing by author.

Experience	Description	Skills Acquired
Soil Testing	Conducting tests like Proctor compaction and Atterberg limits to assess soil properties	Soil analysis, precision, attention to detail
Asphalt Testing	Performing tests such as Marshall stability to ensure road durability	Asphalt quality control, testing procedures
Concrete Testing	Utilizing the Abraham Slump Test and compressive strength tests for concrete assessment	Concrete consistency, workability, strength assessment
CDL Practice	Obtaining a Commercial Driver's License through theoretical and practical driving sessions	Vehicle operation, safety regulations, maneuvering
Surveying	Using instruments like theodolites and GPS units for topographic mapping and site layout	Surveying techniques, accuracy, geometric principles
FEMA Inspections	Assessing damage and compliance post-disasters to ensure structural integrity	Disaster assessment, structural evaluation
Stormwater Inspections	Inspecting stormwater management systems to prevent pollution and manage runoff	Environmental awareness, regulatory compliance